

Thermal-hydraulic investigation of novel thorium-uranium fuel mixtures in advanced SMR assembly configurations

Sinem Uzun¹, Yasin Genç², Hanan Rifai³, Ouadie Kabach⁴, Bedrettin Uzun⁵, Zouhair Sadoune³, El Mahjoub Chakir⁴, Hamid Amsil⁶, Fadi El Banni⁷

¹ Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, Erzincan Binali Yıldırım University, Erzincan, Türkiye

² Ministry of Interior, Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency, Ankara, Türkiye

³ Laboratory of Electronic Systems, Information Processing, Mechanics and Energy, Faculty of Sciences, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco

⁴ Laboratory of Materials and Subatomic Physics, Faculty of Sciences, Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, Morocco

⁵ Republic of Turkey Northeast Anatolia Development Agency, Erzincan, Türkiye

⁶ National Center for Energy, Sciences and Nuclear Technique, Rabat, Morocco

⁷ Institute for Research on New Energies, Nangui Abrogoua University, Abidjan, Cote d'Ivoire

Corresponding author: Ouadie Kabach (ouadie.kabach10@gmail.com)

Academic editor: Kyung O. Kim ♦ Received 15 April 2025 ♦ Accepted 25 September 2025 ♦ Published 7 November 2025

Citation: Uzun S, Genç Y, Rifai H, Kabach O, Uzun B, Sadoune Z, Chakir EM, Amsil H, El Banni F (2025) Thermal-hydraulic investigation of novel thorium-uranium fuel mixtures in advanced SMR assembly configurations. Nuclear Energy and Technology 11(4): 231–241. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.11.167007>

Abstract

Nuclear energy sustainability and deployment flexibility can be significantly enhanced through Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) technology. Critical to their operational success is the thorough assessment of thermal-hydraulic characteristics, especially when incorporating advanced fuel design concepts. This research conducts an extensive thermal-hydraulic analysis examining various thorium-based fuel formulations, including (Th-²³⁵U)O₂, (Th-²³³U)O₂, and an innovative (Th-²³³U-²³⁵U)O₂ composition, benchmarked against standard UO₂ fuel. The investigation encompasses both solid fuel arrangements and dual-cooled annular assembly designs, focusing on safety optimization and operational efficiency enhancement. The analysis focuses on key safety parameters, including pressure drop, coolant enthalpy, fuel centerline temperature, and Departure from Nucleate Boiling Ratio (DNBR). Results for solid fuel configurations reveal that thorium-based fuels exhibit reduced pressure drop, more efficient enthalpy distribution, lower peak fuel temperatures, and higher DNBR values compared to conventional UO₂, highlighting improved thermal stability and safety margins. The (Th-²³³U-²³⁵U)O₂ mixture demonstrates a balanced performance by mitigating the limitations of other thorium compositions. In annular configurations, all fuel types benefit from enhanced heat removal due to the dual cooling surfaces, resulting in further reductions in pressure drop and peak temperatures, as well as a significant increase in DNBR values. The highest DNBR, reaching up to 3.051, confirms the annular geometry's superior safety performance against boiling crises.

Keywords

SMRs, Thorium-based fuel, Annular fuel assembly, Dual-cooled fuel design, Advanced nuclear fuels

Introduction

Nuclear energy plays a crucial role in achieving low carbon emissions and ensuring reliable energy production. While the construction of traditional large-scale nuclear reactors requires high-cost and long-term projects, SMRs stand out as a more flexible, economical, and safe alternative. While SMRs offer faster production and installation opportunities thanks to their modular designs, they can provide advantages, especially in terms of energy supply security, electricity production in remote areas, and industrial applications (Michaelson and Jiang 2021; Luo et al. 2024).

In order for SMRs to operate reliably and efficiently, their thermal management must be analysed in detail. Heat transfer, cooling mechanisms, and thermal performance within the reactor are critical parameters for reactor safety and operating efficiency. In this context, studies on thermal analysis of SMRs contribute to optimizing reactor design and improving safety standards. In a study, the concept of lead-bismuth cooled Super SMR (LSMR) was proposed to increase economic efficiency. In preliminary optimization studies using oxide fuel, it was aimed to improve the neutron impact performance (k_{eff}/SW) according to the separation work (SW). According to the results, the maximum k_{eff}/SW value is mainly related to fuel richness (Chen et al. 2018). In another important study, an experiment was conducted on a 1/3 scale hydraulic model for the SMR. Flow distribution factors and mixing coefficients were obtained by making flow and conductivity measurements at the inlet of the fuel beam simulators. In particular, the effect of velocity on flow distribution and mixing was analysed. The results revealed that the effect of velocity on flow distribution and mixing is limited (Peng et al. 2021).

Since SMR reactors are still quite new, their applicability is not sufficiently developed. In a study, scaling methods used for integrated pressurized water reactor (IPWR) type SMRs, similarity approaches, and possible difficulties were discussed. Additionally, design considerations and previous research to achieve prototypical conditions in test facilities were examined. The results show that appropriate scaling and similarity principles will accelerate the safe and efficient implementation of next-generation SMRs by increasing the reliability of results obtained from non-nuclear test facilities (Bhowmik et al. 2024).

Another study develops a method combining neutronic and thermo-hydraulic properties to evaluate the dimensional change and lifetime of moderator graphite in small modular molten salt reactors (SM-MSR). SM-MSRs have advantages such as flexible core design, high burn rate, and thorium production capacity. However, the dimensional change of graphite is an important factor limiting reactor life. In the study, the dimensional change of graphite was simulated more precisely with the newly developed coupled method. Evaluations show that the critical time points for graphite components to maintain their structural integrity are the 6th and 9th years [6].

While most of the studies on SMR focus on neutronic analyses, the relatively low number of thermal-hydraulic studies is based on several basic scientific and technical reasons. First

of all, the most critical point in the design process of SMRs is to ensure the safe operation of the reactor. Therefore, in the first stage, the neutronic properties of the reactor are examined in detail. Neutronic analyses are the cornerstone of the design, as basic parameters such as fuel composition, enrichment, neutron spectrum, and reactivity coefficients are decisive for the sustainability of the reactor. To ensure the safety of SMRs, the control, criticality, and reactivity coefficients of the chain reaction must first be optimized.

Another important reason why thermal-hydraulic studies are rare is that such analyses are experimentally and computationally more complex. Advanced computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations are needed to model parameters such as heat transfer, multiphase flow, and coolant behaviour. Additionally, experiments for thermal-hydraulic testing of small-scale reactors have scaling problems, making it difficult to directly extrapolate the obtained data to a real-size reactor. In addition, since SMRs are still in the commercialization phase, experimental thermal-hydraulic data sets are quite limited compared to large commercial reactors (Todreas and Kazimi 1990; Yeoh 2019; Zhong et al. 2024).

The priorities of regulatory institutions also cause thermal-hydraulic studies to be carried out relatively less. Organizations such as the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and the US Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) require new reactor designs to primarily meet neutronic safety criteria. Thermal-hydraulic analyses are generally detailed within the scope of safety assessments against accidents, after the design is determined from a neutronic perspective (NRC 2016).

Despite all these disadvantages, there are literature studies that perform thermal analysis for SMR reactors. Kitcher et al. develop a physical model for the SMR based on the integral pressurized water reactor (IPWR) design. Fuel depletion simulations optimize active fuel length, fuel enrichment, and loading pattern to uniform core power distribution. As a result of optimization, 500 MW thermal power and a four-year core life are achieved. When the active fuel length is increased to 240 cm, the capacity factor increases to 95%. For safety, Doppler, moderator temperature, space, and power reactivity coefficients remain at negative values. Thermal analysis shows fuel and cladding temperatures are within the safety margin of industry standards. These results support the safe and efficient operation of SMR (Kitcher and Chirayath 2016). While the term “SMR” has been adopted worldwide to refer to all small reactor designs, there are significant differences between the main types of SMRs under development. These SMR designs, for example, use various refrigerants and fuel forms and have different technology readiness levels (TRLs) and licensing readiness levels (LRLs) (Carelli and Ingersoll 2015; Mignacca and Locatelli 2020; Lloyd et al. 2021; IAEA 2024).

In this context, this study presents a detailed investigation of the thermal-hydraulic behaviour of solid and annular fuel rods in an SMR assembly, building upon our previously published neutronic investigations that established the theoretical foundation for the proposed (Th-²³³U-²³⁵U)O₂ fuel composition (Rifai et al. 2025). This work

provides a comprehensive thermal-hydraulic evaluation of the $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ fuel composition against previously investigated thorium-based alternatives, $(\text{Th-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ and $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$, as well as traditional UO_2 fuel (Benrhnia et al. 2022b; El Banni et al. 2022, 2024; Bouassa et al. 2023, 2024; Lkouz et al. 2023a, 2023b; Kabach et al. 2024; Rifai et al. 2025). The novel $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ formulation strategically incorporates balanced proportions of U-235 and U-233 with Th-232 to overcome the inherent limitations of other thorium-based compositions, particularly the reduced delayed neutron fraction and potentially problematic moderator temperature coefficient behaviour exhibited by $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ fuel, while simultaneously reducing the elevated fissile content requirements of $(\text{Th-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ fuel (Benrhnia et al. 2022a; Bouassa et al. 2024; Kabach et al. 2024; Rifai et al. 2025). Compared to conventional UO_2 , the $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ composition offers substantial non-proliferation benefits by significantly limiting plutonium production and constraining minor actinide formation, while demonstrating enhanced negative fuel temperature coefficients due to Th-232's pronounced resonance absorption characteristics.

All compositions are studied in both solid and dual-cooled annular assembly configurations, with particular emphasis on annular geometries due to their superior thermal performance characteristics, including reduced surface heat flow, decreased peak fuel temperatures by 200–300 K, improved DNBR margins, and enhanced safety during loss-of-coolant accidents compared to traditional solid fuel rods (Shwageraus et al. 2004; Kazimi and Hejzlar 2006; Feng et al. 2007; Hejzlar and Kazimi 2007; Kazimi 2007; Xu et al. 2007; Shin et al. 2012; Koo et al. 2013; Zhang et al. 2021). The dual-cooled annular fuel design presents particularly compelling advantages for LWR-based SMRs, offering enhanced thermal performance that supports extended fuel cycles critical to economic viability, improved passive safety system effectiveness, and superior heat transfer characteristics that directly address the unique operational challenges inherent to small modular reactor systems. This comprehensive thermal-hydraulic assessment examines key thermal safety parameters such as pressure drop, coolant enthalpy, fuel centerline temperature, and DNBR temperature distributions, heat transfer mechanisms, and cooling performance across different fuel compositions and geometries to provide crucial insights for advancing SMR design and operational efficiency.

Methodology and input parameters

Design specifications of the reference SMR

In this study, the Westinghouse AP300™ reactor is adopted as the benchmark design for comparison. As a Generation III+ small modular reactor (SMR), the AP300™ delivers 330 MWe of electrical power from a thermal output of 990 MWth. This design is a scaled-down derivative of the well-established AP1000®, leveraging operational experience and existing regulatory frameworks to minimize technical

uncertainties (Westinghouse Electric Company LLC 2023; IAEA 2024). The reactor core is composed of 121 assemblies arranged in a 17×17 lattice structure, typically utilizing uranium dioxide (UO_2) fuel with an enrichment of U-235 below 5 wt.%. Each assembly contains 264 fuel rods based on the robust Westinghouse 17×17 fuel design. The AP300 is engineered for long operating cycles of up to 36 months, with possible extensions to 48 months, thereby reducing the frequency of refuelling compared to conventional reactors. Reactivity control is achieved using a combination of control rods and soluble boron (Westinghouse Electric Company LLC 2004; Schulz 2006; Laranjo de Stefani et al. 2019; Rifai et al. 2025). Table 1 presents the key design specifications.

Table 1. Key design specifications (IAEA 2024, Rifai et al. 2025)

Design Parameter	Specification
Reactor technology	PWR SMR
Coolant System/Moderator	Water
Generation Capacity (Thermal/Electrical), MW _t /MW _e	990/330
Primary Coolant Circulation	Forced flow with 2 reactor coolant pumps
Operating Pressure Levels (Primary/Secondary), kPa	15,400/7,350
Core Temperature Conditions (Inlet/Outlet), K	575.15/598.15
Fuel Configuration/Lattice Structure	UO_2 fuel / 17×17 square lattice
Fuel Assembly Quantity	121
Fissile Material Content (%)	Less than 5 wt.% U-235 in U
Refueling Interval (months)	36 (up to 48)
Control System Approach	Rods, soluble boron
Safety Philosophy	Passive (as in the AP1000)
Design life (years)	80

Benchmark assembly characteristics and proposed fuel concepts

The majority of the proposed small modular pressurized water reactors typically utilize conventional solid cylindrical UO_2 fuel rods, housed within zirconium-alloy cladding and arranged in a 17×17 lattice configuration. However, the compact nature of SMR cores introduces unique thermal-hydraulic behavior and non-uniform power distribution, prompting the need to re-evaluate traditional fuel assembly designs, fuel loading strategies, and associated performance metrics. While solid UO_2 pellets have proven effective in large-scale reactors, they are inherently limited by their thermal properties, particularly the tendency for heat to accumulate along the centerline of the fuel rod. This phenomenon imposes constraints on potential power uprates due to thermal stress and safety margins (YANG et al. 2009; Shin et al. 2012; Zhang et al. 2021).

As outlined in previous studies (Hejzlar and Kazimi 2007; Ansarifard and Ebrahimian 2016), annular fuel with dual coolant channels offers significant advantages for addressing these challenges. By reducing the radial thickness of the fuel and introducing both internal and external coolant paths, peak temperatures within the fuel matrix are markedly decreased. This design enhances heat removal efficiency and increases the surface area for heat transfer, thereby lowering the thermal load on the cladding and improving the departure from nucleate boiling (DNB) safety margin. The additional moderation afforded by the surrounding coolant also supports improved neutron thermalization, which can translate into higher allowable power densities (Hejzlar and

Kazimi 2007; Ansarifar and Ebrahimian 2016). This innovative geometry introduces two separate fuel-to-cladding gaps and multiple flow paths (see Fig. 1), contributing to superior thermal control. Such improvements in heat management can potentially extend fuel residence time by reducing temperature-driven degradation—an especially beneficial feature when considering thorium-fueled SMRs, where minimizing refueling frequency is a key operational goal. In this context, several studies have examined the feasibility of implementing annular dual-cooled fuel designs within SMR platforms such as NuScale. Investigations by Zaidabadi Nejad, Ansarifar, and Zhang et al. have demonstrated encouraging results for this approach (Ansarifar and Ebrahimian 2016; Nejad and Ansarifar 2020; Zaidabadi Nejad and Ansarifar 2020). Of particular interest is the work of Kazimi and Hejzlar, who reported that a 13×13 fuel lattice with 9 guide tubes in a dual-cooled configuration offers outstanding performance metrics. This assembly configuration, according to Kazimi and Hejzlar, enables higher coolant flow rates and supports up to 50% greater power output, all while maintaining better mechanical stability compared to conventional solid-fuel assemblies (Kazimi and Hejzlar 2006).

Figure 1. Cross-sectional view of annular fuel rod with dual cooling arrangement (Koo et al. 2013).

Building upon the foundational concepts introduced earlier, our prior studies have investigated the feasibility of utilizing $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ as an advanced nuclear fuel option. This particular fuel formulation integrates Th-232 with recovered U-233 and reprocessed U-235, aiming to leverage the synergistic benefits of both fissile uranium isotopes (Benrhnia et al. 2022b, 2022a; Bouassa et al. 2023, 2024; Lkouz et al. 2023b). Unlike earlier research efforts that primarily addressed in depth neutronic behavior, the current study concentrates thermal-hydraulic performance within the most demanding (hot channel) conditions at the assembly scale this include key thermal safety parameters such as pressure drop, coolant enthalpy, fuel centerline temperature, and DNBR temperature distributions, heat transfer

mechanisms, and cooling performance across different fuel compositions and geometries to provide crucial insights for advancing SMR design and operational efficiency.

As previously discussed, this evaluation considers the proposed $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ composition alongside conventional UO_2 fuel and two reference thorium-based fuels: $(\text{Th-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ and $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ (Fig. 2). Table 2 summarizes the fundamental material and isotopic properties of the investigated fuel types, while Table 3 details the principal geometric and design parameters associated with the corresponding fuel assembly configurations.

Table 2. Properties of the analyzed fuel type (Herring and MacDonald 1999, IAEA 2008, Rifai et al. 2025)

Fuel	Density (g/cm ³)	Fissile enrichment (wt.%)
UO_2	10.412 (95% of TD)	4.95% (U-235)
$(\text{Th-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$	9.50 (95% of TD)	4.95% (U-235)
$(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$	9.50 (95% of TD)	4.95% (U-233)
$(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$	9.50 (95% of TD)	2.475% (U-233) + 2.475% (U-235)

TD is the theoretical density.

Table 3. Assembly-level parameters considered in the simulations (Hejzlar and Kazimi 2007, Hassan et al. 2019, Zhang et al. 2021)

System parameter	Standard design	Dual-cooled design
Rod matrix layout	17×17	13×13
Total fuel elements	264	160
Guide tube count	24	9
Assembly center-to-center distance (cm)	21.5	21.5
Pin-to-pin distance (cm)	1.26	1.65
Inner clad interior radius (cm)	-	0.4315
Inner clad exterior radius (cm)	-	0.4887
Inner gap boundary radius (cm)	-	0.4969
Fuel pellet outer radius (cm)	0.4096	0.7031
Outer gap outer radius (cm)	0.4178	0.7113
Outer clad exterior radius (cm)	0.4750	0.7685
Fuel volume per fuel rod (cm ³)	1339.04	1974.89
Total fuel volume per assembly (cm ³)	353506.73	315983.02
Guide structure inner radius (cm)	0.56	0.71
Guide structure outer radius (cm)	0.60	0.77

Thermal hydraulics modelling

In this study, the Monte Carlo N-Particle (MCNP) code was employed to perform power distribution calculations, which were used to identify the hot channel for subsequent thermal-hydraulic analysis. MCNP, a Monte Carlo-based simulation tool, is widely applied in nuclear engineering for core neutronic evaluations, shielding assessments, radiation transport, detector modeling, and particle interaction studies (Werner 2017; Hassan et al. 2019). Each MCNP run was performed with 300 active cycles and 100,000 neutron histories per cycle, yielding a total of 30 million particle histories. Under these conditions, the statistical uncertainty remained below 11 pcm in most cases, with the maximum

Figure 2. Horizontal cross-sectional view of the modeled solid and annular assembly and fuel pins (Rifai et al. 2025).

reported uncertainty reaching 14 pcm. The overall results remain statistically reliable for the purposes of this study.

A dedicated thermal-hydraulic model was developed to evaluate heat transfer mechanisms in a representative fuel channel of an SMR, considering both solid and annular fuel geometries. The model treats the fuel, cladding, and coolant as distinct domains, with volumetric heat generation assumed uniformly within the fuel region. Energy is conducted radially through the cladding and removed via convection at the fuel–coolant interface, with temperature-dependent thermophysical properties (thermal conductivity, specific heat, and density) incorporated for fuel and cladding materials. The geometric configurations of both fuel types are based on conventional PWR assemblies, reflecting the technological continuity with large-scale reactors, though adapted with reduced active fuel length to suit SMR compact core dimensions (Kitcher and Chirayath 2016). A single-channel analysis framework was employed, focusing on the “hot channel”—the most thermally limiting region of the core—to conservatively estimate key safety parameters such as peak fuel temperature, pressure drop, heat flux, and DNBR (NRC 2007; Ghazanfari et al. 2016). For annular fuel, enhanced heat removal due to dual-surface cooling was accounted for by modifying the surface area and convective coefficients (see Fig. 3). Additionally, subchannel analysis principles were applied to discretize the coolant flow and solve the conservation equations of mass, momentum, and energy under steady-state, single-phase flow conditions (Todreas and Kazimi 1990; Ghazanfari et al. 2016). Pressure drop and convective heat transfer were modeled using simplified hydraulic correlations and Dittus-Boelter-type relations, respectively. This methodology was used to compare the thermal performance of four fuel compositions, as detailed in Table 2.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{v}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho h)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho h \vec{v}) = -\nabla \cdot \vec{q} + \dot{q} + \frac{\partial(\rho p)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (p \vec{v}) + \tau \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \vec{v})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{v} \vec{v}) = \nabla \cdot p + \nabla \tau + \rho g \quad (3)$$

In equations (1–3), ρ represents the fluid density, \vec{v} denotes the velocity vector, $\frac{\partial(\rho)}{\partial t}$ indicates the time-dependent change in density, and $\nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{v})$ expresses the mass flux entering or leaving a control volume. And ρv represents the momentum density, $\nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{v} \vec{v})$ denotes the convective transport of momentum, $\nabla \cdot p$ refers to the pressure forces, $\nabla \tau$ accounts for viscous (shear) stresses, and ρg corresponds to body forces such as gravity.

Thermal hydraulics analysis results

The thermal-hydraulic analyses in this study were performed using an in-house MATLAB-based subchannel-type computational model developed by the authors. This model solves the one-dimensional discretized conservation equations of mass, momentum, and energy along the coolant channel. The model allows for the parametric definition of the fuel geometry, enabling the simulation of both solid and annular

Figure 3. MCNP Models for thermal-hydraulic assessment.

fuel configurations by specifying the inner and outer surface heat-transfer boundary conditions. Accordingly, COBRA-IV was employed only for benchmarking the single-phase pressure-drop behavior in solid fuel geometry, whereas all annular fuel analyses were conducted using the developed in-house channel model. The thermal-hydraulic parameters were then evaluated through the one-dimensional single-channel formulation. The pressure drop was computed using the Darcy–Weisbach equation with an appropriate friction factor correlation as a function of the Reynolds number, while the coolant enthalpy was determined from the axial energy balance along the channel, as presented in Eq. (4).

$$\frac{dh}{dz} = \frac{q'' \cdot P}{\dot{m}} \quad (4)$$

In Eq. 4., q'' is the surface heat flux, P is the wetted perimeter, and \dot{m} is the mass flow rate. The coolant temperature distribution was obtained from the enthalpy using temperature-dependent thermophysical properties, while the radial fuel temperature profile was calculated by solving the steady-state conduction equation in cylindrical coordinates. DNBR was defined as the ratio of the local critical heat flux to the actual surface heat flux, and it is given in Eq. 5.

$$\text{DNBR} = \frac{q''_{\text{CHF}}}{q''_{\text{actual}}} \quad (5)$$

In this study, the CHF values used for DNBR evaluation were obtained using the W-3 correlation, which expresses the critical heat flux as a function of mass flux, pressure, and vapor quality:

$$q'' = CG^m h_{fg} \left(\frac{P}{P_c} \right)^n f(x) \quad (6)$$

where C is an empirical constant, G is the mass flux, h_{fg} is the latent heat of vaporization, P is the local pressure, P_c is the critical pressure, and $f(x)$ is a correction function of vapor quality.

Fig. 4 presents the pressure profiles along the fuel channel for four different fuel compositions. The results show modest but consistent differences depending on the fuel type. The UO_2 case exhibits a pressure drop of approximately 1.4 kPa, while thorium-based fuels show

Figure 4. Pressure drop values for the investigated the solid fuel models.

slightly lower values in the range of 1.1–1.2 kPa. This indicates a small hydraulic advantage for the thorium-based fuels, which could translate into reduced pumping power requirements and improved system efficiency. Although the general trends are similar across all fuels, the step-wise nature of the curves arises from the discretization of the coolant channel into finite axial segments in the thermal-hydraulic model, where pressure losses are calculated incrementally. While this produces a piecewise appearance, the overall behavior corresponds to a smooth pressure drop along the channel.

Fig. 5 shows the enthalpy profiles along the channel, highlighting the evolution of the coolant's energy content as a function of fuel type. Enthalpy is directly linked to coolant temperature and pressure and provides a key indicator of thermal energy transport. Among the cases analyzed, UO_2 exhibits the highest outlet enthalpy at approximately 1500 kJ/kg, compared to about 1480 kJ/kg for $(\text{Th}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$, in agreement with the figure. While the difference is modest, it reflects the slightly higher thermal conversion achieved with UO_2 under the same operating conditions. These results confirm that thorium-based fuels maintain competitive thermal-hydraulic performance while offering recognized advantages in long-term fuel cycle performance.

Figure 5. Enthalpy values for the solid fuel models.

Fig. 6 provides insight into the temperature distribution within the reactor core for each fuel type. The system using UO_2 fuel demonstrates the highest peak temperatures,

consistent with its higher volumetric power density. A typical radial temperature gradient- decreasing from the fuel centerline toward the cladding- is observed, confirming conduction-dominated heat transfer. Thorium-based fuels, in contrast, result in lower peak temperatures, indicating a more thermally stable behaviour under the same operating conditions. The degree of temperature uniformity is crucial for avoiding thermal stresses in fuel and cladding materials, highlighting the potential safety advantage of mixed thorium fuel systems. The $(\text{Th}^{233}\text{U}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ mixture exhibits fuel temperatures that are essentially comparable to UO_2 , with marginally lower peak values. This indicates that the novel thorium-based fuel does not compromise thermal safety margins compared to conventional UO_2 .

Figure 6. Temperature values for the solid fuel models.

Fig. 7 presents the DNBR, a key safety metric that indicates the margin to critical heat flux and the potential onset of nucleate boiling crisis. All fuel types maintain DNBR values well above the safety threshold, confirming thermal margin sufficiency under the simulated conditions. However, the UO_2 fuel case shows relatively lower DNBR values, reflecting its higher heat flux and peak temperatures. In contrast, the thorium-based fuel combinations achieve higher DNBR values, implying a greater safety buffer against boiling transition. This outcome reinforces the thermal safety advantage of incorporating thorium into the fuel matrix. Specifically, the DNBR value for UO_2 approaches 2.45, whereas thorium-based fuels achieve values up to 2.75, clearly illustrating the enhanced safety margin offered by advanced fuel designs.

In this study, the DNBR values were evaluated using the W-3 correlation, which is one of the most widely adopted CHF correlations for pressurized water reactor conditions. The W-3 correlation estimates the CHF as a function of mass flux, pressure, and vapor quality, and has been extensively validated for PWR-type rod-bundle geometries. Since DNBR is defined as the ratio of the predicted CHF to the actual surface heat flux, even small changes in the local heat flux distribution among different fuel types result in noticeable variations in DNBR values, although the enthalpy and temperature profiles remain nearly identical.

The analyses in Figs 4–7 reveal that different fuel types create significant differences not only in terms of neutronic

Figure 7. DNBR values for the solid fuel models.

performance but also in terms of thermohydraulic behaviour. Thorium-based fuels in particular seem to be promising in terms of thermal safety with their more stable temperature distribution, higher enthalpy, and DNBR values. Therefore, when selecting fuels for SMR systems, not only reactivity and combustion properties but also heat transfer capacity and safety margins should be taken into account.

Fig. 8 shows the pressure drop graph for annular fuel (for the outer channel). The maximum pressure drop of 1.4 kPa in solid fuel is reduced to approximately 1.2–1.25 kPa with annular geometry. This reduces the pumping power requirement, increasing the energy efficiency of the system. Fig. 9 shows the enthalpy change in annular fuel. Especially with fuels with high neutron efficiency, such as $(Th-^{233}U)O_2$, further enthalpy increases are expected.

Figure 8. Pressure drop values for the investigated annular fuel models.

Figure 9. Enthalpy values for the annular fuel models.

The temperature distribution is shown in Fig. 10. The fuel temperature distribution along the channel height, as shown in the temperature profile graph, reveals the characteristic thermal behaviour of annular fuel elements. Due to the dual-surface cooling design (where both the inner and outer surfaces of the fuel are exposed to coolant flow), the radial heat conduction path is significantly reduced compared to solid fuel configurations. This geometric advantage leads to lower peak fuel temperatures and a more uniform radial temperature gradient. The profile exhibits a parabolic shape, with maximum temperatures observed near the mid-height of the channel. This behaviour aligns with the axial power distribution commonly present in reactor cores, where power density tends to peak at the center and decreases toward the inlet and outlet. Offering enhanced safety margins against thermal stresses, fuel melting, and cladding degradation.

Figure 10. Temperature values for the annular fuel model.

The DNBR profile illustrates the margin between operating heat flux and the CHF along the channel height (Fig. 11). Although the pressure and temperature profiles along the channel remain very similar for all fuel types due to the identical boundary conditions, DNBR exhibits noticeable differences. This is because DNBR is defined as the ratio of the CHF to the actual surface heat flux, rather than a direct function of bulk pressure or temperature. The CHF was evaluated using the W-3 correlation, which strongly depends on local heat flux, mass flux, and quality. Even small variations in the power distribution and heat generation among the fuels, therefore, lead to appreciable changes in DNBR, despite the similarity of pressure and temperature trends. In the case of annular fuel, the increased heat transfer surface area and improved convective cooling result in a significant enhancement of the DNBR value throughout the channel. The profiles show a gradually increasing trend with height, reflecting the progressive rise in coolant temperature and heat flux absorption along the flow direction. This behaviour is physically consistent, as the coolant becomes less efficient at absorbing heat near the outlet due to its elevated temperature, yet the annular geometry compensates for this by maintaining surface temperatures at relatively lower levels. Among the four cases, $Annular_{(Th-^{235}U)O_2}$ exhibits the highest DNBR values, peaking around 3.051, whereas $Annular_{(Th-^{233}U)O_2}$

Figure 11. DNBR values for the annular fuel model.

reaches approximately 2.381. All values remain safely above the industry-standard safety threshold (typically $\text{DNBR} > 1.3\text{--}1.4$), confirming that the annular design not only improves thermal efficiency but also significantly enhances boiling crisis prevention capabilities.

Conclusion

In this study, a comprehensive thermal-hydraulic analysis was performed to evaluate the performance of

different nuclear fuel compositions: UO_2 , $(\text{Th-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$, $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$, and $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ within solid and annular fuel geometries under SMR operating conditions. By modeling the coupled heat conduction and convection mechanisms along the axial direction of the fuel channel, key thermal safety parameters, including pressure drop, coolant enthalpy, fuel centerline temperature, and DNBR, were assessed. The results indicate that the annular fuel geometry exhibits a slightly lower peak temperature (approximately 3 K) compared to the solid design, and this difference falls within the uncertainty limits of the analysis. Even so, the annular configuration provides higher DNBR values and a lower pressure drop, indicating better coolant flow and wider thermal safety margins compared to the solid geometry. Among the fuels analyzed, thorium-based compositions, particularly the $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ mixture, demonstrated favorable thermal-hydraulic behavior, with lower fuel temperatures and higher DNBR values relative to conventional UO_2 . This suggests that combining advanced thorium-based fuels with annular geometry can enhance both performance and operational safety in next-generation compact reactor systems. The developed model provides a solid foundation for further parametric studies and can support future simulation-driven design optimization.

References

- Ansarifar GR, Ebrahimian M (2016) Design and neutronic investigation of the Nano fluids application to VVER-1000 nuclear reactor with dual cooled annular fuel. *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 87: 39–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2015.08.013>
- El Banni F, Gogon BLH, Kabach O, Chakir EM (2024) Analyzing $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ fuel performance in various assembly configurations: A comparative neutronic study. *Nuclear Energy and Technology* 10: 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.3897/nucet.10.125376>
- El Banni F, Kabach O, Boko A, Gogon BLH, Koua AA, Monnehan GA, Benchrif A, Amsil H, Chetaine A (2022) Neutronic investigation of a VVER-1200 $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ fuel assembly with protactinium oxide as a burnable absorber coated on the outer surface of the fuel rods. *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects* 44: 7650–7664. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2022.2116506>
- Benrhnia Z, Kabach O, Chetaine A, Saidi A (2022a) Analysis of reactivity control coefficients and the stability of an AP1000 reactor assembly fueled with $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ using DRAGON code. *Annals of the University of Craiova, Physics* 32: 88–102.
- Benrhnia Z, Chetaine A, Kabach O, Amsil H, Benchrif A, El Banni F (2022b) Neutronic and burnup characteristics of potential dual-cooled annular $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ fuel for the advanced pressurized water reactors: An assembly-level analysis. *International Journal of Energy Research* 46: 23501–23516. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.8648>
- Bhowmik PK, Sabharwall P, Johnson JT, Retamales MET, Wang C, O'Brien JE, Lietwiler C, Wu Q (2024) Scaling methodologies and similarity analysis for thermal hydraulics test facility development for water-cooled small modular reactor. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 424: 113235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2024.113235>
- Bouassa T, Kabach O, Chakir EM (2024) Neutronic analysis of different sandwich cladding material options for $(\text{Th-}^{233}\text{U-}^{235}\text{U})\text{O}_2$ annular fuel in advanced PWR assembly. *Interactions* 245: 239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10751-024-02094-7>
- Bouassa T, Kabach O, Chetaine A, Benrhnia Z, El Banni F, Saidi A (2023) Parametric neutronic analysis of different cladding options for ThO_2 pellet of advanced dual-cooled annular PWR assembly. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 414: 112533. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2023.112533>
- Carelli MD, Ingersoll DT (2015) Woodhead Publishing Series in Energy: Number 64 Handbook of Small Modular Nuclear Reactors. Elsevier (Ed.) Woodhead Publishing.
- Chen Z, Lv Z, Zhao ZJ, Yuan B, Tian L, Jiang J (2018) Core optimization of 5 MWth Lead-bismuth cooled Super small Module Reactor (LSMR) based on separate work. *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 120: 735–741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2018.06.030>
- Feng D, Hejzlar P, Kazimi MS (2007) Thermal-Hydraulic Design of High-Power-Density Annular Fuel in PWRs. *Nuclear Technology* 160: 16–44. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT07-A3882>
- Ghazanfari V, Talebi M, Khorsandi J, Abdolahi R (2016) Effects of water based Al_2O_3 , TiO_2 , and CuO nanofluids as the coolant on solid and annular fuels for a typical VVER-1000 core. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 91: 285–294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2016.05.007>
- Hassan IA, Badawi AA, El Saghir A, Shaat MK (2019) Viability of uranium nitride (UN) as annular fuel for AP-1000. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 110: 170–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2018.09.020>

- Hejzlar P, Kazimi MS (2007) Annular fuel for high-power-density pressurized water reactors: Motivation and overview. *Nuclear Technology* 160: 2–15. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT160-2-15>
- Herring JS, MacDonald PE (1999) ANS annual meeting Characteristics of mixed Thorium – Uranium dioxide high burnup fuel.
- IAEA (2008) Thermophysical Properties of Materials For Nuclear Engineering: A Tutorial and Collection of Data Thermophysical Properties of Materials For Nuclear Engineering: A Tutorial and Collection of Data. https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/IAEA-THPH_web.pdf
- IAEA (2024) Small Modular Reactor Technology Catalogue. https://aris.iaea.org/Publications/SMR_catalogue_2024.pdf#page=19.08
- Kabach O, Mahjoub Chakir E, Amsil H (2024) Innovative burnable absorbers: Assessing PaO₂ and NpO₂ coatings for improved safety in (Th-233U-235U)O₂ fuel assemblies. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 421: 113086. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2024.113086>
- Kazimi MS (2007) Introduction to the annular fuel special issue. *Nuclear Technology* 160: 1. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT160-1-1>
- Kazimi MS, Hejzlar P (2006) High Performance Fuel Design for Next Generation PWRs: Final Report.
- Kitcher ED, Chirayath SS (2016) Neutronics and thermal hydraulics analysis of a small modular reactor. *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 97: 232–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2016.07.019>
- Koo Y-H, Yang J-H, Park J-Y, Yang Y-S (2013) Status of Dual Cooled Annular Fuel Development in KAERI. In: 2013 EHPG. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/259127932_Status_of_Dual_Cooled_Annular_Fuel_Development_in_KAERI
- Laranjo de Stefani G, Losada Moreira JM, Maiorino JR, Russo Rossi PC (2019) Detailed neutronic calculations of the AP1000 reactor core with the Serpent code. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 116: 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2019.03.030>
- Lkouz M, Kabach O, Chetaine A (2023a) Enhancing temperature reactivity coefficients in SMR Reactor with (Th233U-235U)2 fuel through PaO₂ as a burnable absorber. *Annals of the University of Craiova, Physics* 33: 181–190.
- Lkouz M, Kabach O, Chetaine A, Saidi A, Bouassa T (2023b) Revolutionizing LWR SMR reactors: exploring the potential of (Th-233U-235U)O₂ fuel through a parametric study. *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects* 45: 10162–10175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2023.2243859>
- Lloyd CA, Roulstone T, Lyons RE (2021) Transport, constructability, and economic advantages of SMR modularization. *Progress in Nuclear Energy* 134: 103672. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2021.103672>
- Luo R, Li Y, Guo H, Wang Q, Wang X (2024) Cross-operating-condition fault diagnosis of a small module reactor based on CNN-LSTM transfer learning with limited data. *Energy* 313: 133901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.133901>
- Michaelson D, Jiang J (2021) Review of integration of small modular reactors in renewable energy microgrids. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 152: 111638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111638>
- Mignacca B, Locatelli G (2020) Economics and finance of Small Modular Reactors: A systematic review and research agenda. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 118: 109519. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109519>
- Nejad MZ, Ansarifard GR (2020) Optimal design of a Small Modular Reactor core with dual cooled annular fuel based on the neutronics and natural circulation parameters. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 360: 110518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2020.110518>
- NRC (2007) Chapter 4.4: Thermal and Hydraulic Design. <https://www.nrc.gov/reading-rm/doc-collections/nuregs/staff/sr0800/ch4/index.html>
- NRC (2016) Design-Specific Review Standard for NuScale SMR Design.
- Peng F, Su Q, Xing J, Lu D, Wang C, Gu H (2021) Experimental study on flow distribution and mixing at the core inlet of double-loop small module reactor. *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 152: 108010. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2020.108010>
- Rifai H, Kabach O, Sadoune Z, Chakir EM, Uzun S, Amsil H, Banni F El (2025) Innovative thorium-based fuel assemblies for LW-SMR: In-depth assembly-level neutronic analysis and safety considerations in solid and annular configurations. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 442: 114274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2025.114274>
- Schulz TL (2006) Westinghouse AP1000 advanced passive plant. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 236: 1547–1557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2006.03.049>
- Shin CH, Chun TH, Oh DS, In WK (2012) Thermal hydraulic performance assessment of dual-cooled annular nuclear fuel for OPR-1000. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 243: 291–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2011.12.010>
- Shwageraus E, Hejzlar P, Kazimi MS (2004) Use of Thorium for Transmutation of Plutonium and Minor Actinides in PWRs. *Nuclear Technology* 147: 53–68. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT04-A3514>
- Todreas NE, Kazimi MS (1990) Taylor & Francis Nuclear Systems I: Thermal Hydraulic Fundamentals. Vol. 1. 705 pp.
- Werner CJ (2017) MCNP® USER'S MANUAL Code Version 6.2.
- Westinghouse Electric Company LLC (2004) Chapter 4.3 Nuclear Design AP1000 DCD. <https://www.nrc.gov/docs/ML0507/ML050750282.pdf>
- Westinghouse Electric Company LLC (2023) AP300TM Small Modular Reactor. <https://www.westinghousenuclear.com/energy-systems/ap300-smr> [May 19, 2023]
- Xu Z, Otsuka Y, Hejzlar P, Kazimi MS, Driscoll MJ (2007) High-performance annular fuel reactor physics and fuel management. *Nuclear Technology* 160: 63–79. <https://doi.org/10.13182/NT07-A3884>
- YANG YS, SHIN CH, CHUN TH, SONG KW (2009) Evaluation of a Dual-Cooled Annular Fuel Heat Split and Temperature Distribution. *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology* 46: 836–845. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18811248.2007.9711593>
- Yeoh GH (2019) Thermal hydraulic considerations of nuclear reactor systems: Past, present and future challenges. *Experimental and Computational Multiphase Flow* 1: 3–27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42757-019-0002-5>
- Zaidabadi Nejad M, Ansarifard GR (2020) Design of a Small Modular Nuclear Reactor with dual cooled annular fuel and investigation of the fuel inner radius effect on the power peaking factor and natural circulation parameters. *Annals of Nuclear Energy* 138: 107185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2019.107185>
- Zhang Z, Wu T, Wang Y, Chen S, Yuan C, Zhu J (2021) Core design and neutronic study on a small reactor with advanced fuel designs. *Nuclear Materials and Energy* 29: 101068. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nme.2021.101068>
- Zhong Y, Wang Q, Zou C, Zhu G, Guo W, Wang Z, Wang Y (2024) Neutronics and thermal-hydraulics coupled analysis on dimensional change and lifespan of graphite components in small modular molten salt reactor. *Nuclear Engineering and Design* 425: 113344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2024.113344>

Appendix 1

Sample data table for solid and annular fuel cases

Tabulated below are the computed Thermal hydraulics analysis results for solid and annular cases discussed in this paper.

Table A1. Pressure drop values for the investigated solid (a) and annular (b) fuel models

(a)				
Distance (m)	Solid_UO ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	111.464	111.451	111.449	111.462
0.122	109.980	109.967	109.964	109.977
0.244	99.613	99.600	99.598	99.610
0.366	98.118	98.105	98.103	98.116
0.488	87.697	87.685	87.682	87.695
0.610	86.203	86.190	86.188	86.200
0.732	75.736	75.723	75.721	75.733
0.853	74.239	74.227	74.225	74.236
0.975	63.718	63.707	63.705	63.715
1.097	62.216	62.205	62.204	62.214
1.219	51.644	51.634	51.633	51.642
1.341	50.145	50.136	50.134	50.143
1.463	39.521	39.513	39.512	39.520
1.585	38.020	38.014	38.012	38.019
1.707	27.343	27.338	27.337	27.342
1.829	25.850	25.845	25.844	25.849
1.951	15.139	15.136	15.135	15.138
2.073	4.416	4.415	4.415	4.416
2.195	2.940	2.939	2.939	2.940
2.316	1.467	1.467	1.467	1.467
2.438	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
(b)				
Distance (m)	Annular_UO ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	111.464	111.474	111.446	111.465
0.122	108.848	108.864	108.807	108.456
0.244	98.644	98.355	98.959	98.857
0.366	97.747	97.455	97.060	97.457
0.488	88.937	88.455	88.958	88.343
0.610	85.949	85.685	85.554	85.954
0.732	74.746	74.745	74.098	74.746
0.853	73.835	73.453	73.095	72.835
0.975	62.848	62.454	62.059	62.844
1.097	61.435	61.446	61.445	61.434
1.219	52.849	52.454	52.342	52.834
1.341	50.194	50.554	51.094	50.194
1.463	38.955	38.946	38.847	38.946
1.585	37.023	37.055	37.232	37.344
1.707	26.847	26.848	26.343	26.457
1.829	25.847	25.848	25.433	25.858
1.951	14.938	14.937	14.434	14.946
2.073	3.785	3.768	3.734	3.455
2.195	2.748	2.749	2.323	2.485
2.316	1.454	1.496	1.354	1.499
2.438	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Table A2. Enthalpy values in kJ/kg for the investigated solid (a) and annular (b) fuel models

(a)				
Distance (m)	Solid_UO ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	1283.440	1283.440	1283.440	1283.440
0.122	1286.836	1286.790	1286.790	1286.813
0.244	1292.675	1292.558	1292.558	1292.651
0.366	1300.071	1299.908	1299.885	1300.048
0.488	1309.282	1309.003	1308.980	1309.236
0.610	1320.121	1319.726	1319.703	1320.052
0.732	1332.356	1331.844	1331.821	1332.286
0.853	1345.800	1345.126	1345.079	1345.684
0.975	1360.129	1359.314	1359.268	1360.012
1.097	1375.108	1374.131	1374.061	1374.968
1.219	1390.436	1389.273	1389.204	1390.250
1.341	1405.788	1404.485	1404.369	1405.602
1.463	1420.860	1419.395	1419.279	1420.651
1.585	1435.421	1433.770	1433.653	1435.165
1.707	1449.051	1447.260	1447.144	1448.772
1.829	1461.519	1459.612	1459.472	1461.240
1.951	1472.567	1470.544	1470.404	1472.265
2.073	1481.988	1479.848	1479.708	1481.662
2.195	1489.570	1487.337	1487.175	1489.222
2.316	1495.525	1493.245	1493.083	1495.176
2.438	1498.898	1496.595	1496.409	1498.549
(b)				
Distance (m)	Annular_UO ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	1283.440	1283.445	1283.440	1283.340
0.122	1285.836	1285.565	1285.836	1285.844
0.244	1290.675	1290.645	1290.672	1290.645
0.366	1300.071	1300.075	1300.071	1300.072
0.488	1307.282	1307.254	1307.282	1307.283
0.610	1318.121	1318.145	1318.121	1318.128
0.732	1327.356	1327.354	1327.356	1327.357
0.853	1340.800	1340.854	1340.800	1340.800
0.975	1350.129	1350.145	1350.125	1350.129
1.097	1364.108	1364.105	1364.108	1364.108
1.219	1373.436	1371.445	1371.436	1371.437
1.341	1387.788	1387.754	1387.787	1387.788
1.463	1397.794	1400.794	1400.794	1400.779
1.585	1406.195	1407.195	1407.455	1407.195
1.707	1412.597	1412.597	1412.545	1412.597
1.829	1420.998	1420.998	1420.435	1420.998
1.951	1428.399	1428.395	1428.345	1428.398
2.073	1435.800	1435.805	1435.544	1435.868
2.195	1442.202	1442.202	1442.534	1442.202
2.316	1456.603	1456.603	1456.455	1456.603
2.438	1468.004	1468.004	1468.045	1468.007

Table A3. Temperature values in K for the investigated solid (a) and annular (b) fuel models

(a)				
Distance (m)	Solid_UO ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	562.039	562.039	562.039	562.039
0.122	562.661	562.656	562.656	562.661
0.244	563.733	563.717	563.717	563.728
0.366	565.094	565.061	565.061	565.089
0.488	566.778	566.728	566.728	566.772
0.610	568.767	568.700	568.694	568.756
0.732	571.011	570.922	570.911	571.000
0.853	573.478	573.356	573.350	573.461
0.975	575.956	575.817	575.806	575.933
1.097	578.544	578.378	578.361	578.522
1.219	581.189	580.989	580.978	581.161
1.341	583.844	583.617	583.600	583.811
1.463	586.450	586.194	586.178	586.411
1.585	588.822	588.556	588.539	588.783
1.707	591.033	590.744	590.722	590.989
1.829	593.056	592.744	592.722	593.006
1.951	594.844	594.517	594.494	594.794
2.073	596.372	596.028	596.000	596.317
2.195	597.600	597.239	597.211	597.544
2.316	598.550	598.194	598.167	598.494
2.438	599.056	598.711	598.683	599.006
(b)				
Distance (m)	Annular_UO ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	562.039	562.032	562.039	562.039
0.122	562.656	562.656	562.646	562.662
0.244	563.734	563.712	563.948	563.725
0.366	565.094	565.061	565.095	565.068
0.488	566.746	566.725	566.985	566.736
0.610	568.746	568.445	568.847	568.756
0.732	570.375	570.373	570.948	570.375
0.853	571.738	571.654	571.454	571.735
0.975	573.253	573.144	573.435	573.568
1.097	574.763	574.635	574.436	574.747
1.219	576.234	576.126	576.455	576.250
1.341	577.322	577.618	577.456	577.754
1.463	579.235	579.101	579.068	579.258
1.585	580.753	580.599	580.587	580.762
1.707	582.295	582.091	582.071	582.267
1.829	583.853	583.584	583.560	583.771
1.951	585.304	585.073	585.050	585.275
2.073	586.812	586.454	586.557	586.779
2.195	588.313	588.055	588.029	588.283
2.316	589.825	589.546	589.518	589.790
2.438	591.331	591.037	591.008	591.292

Table A4. DNBR values for the investigated solid (a) and annular (b) fuel models

(a)				
Distance (m)	Solid_UO ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Solid_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	15.064	19.000	13.000	14.000
0.122	8.617	17.495	11.838	12.002
0.244	6.738	10.009	7.022	7.122
0.366	5.317	7.828	5.497	5.579
0.488	4.427	6.178	4.427	4.496
0.610	3.816	5.146	3.695	3.757
0.732	3.387	4.437	3.235	3.291
0.853	3.069	3.939	2.883	2.936
0.975	2.851	3.570	2.646	2.698
1.097	2.707	3.319	2.471	2.522
1.219	2.602	3.136	2.378	2.417
1.341	2.532	3.026	2.304	2.353
1.463	2.511	2.951	2.281	2.335
1.585	2.539	2.929	2.286	2.345
1.707	2.634	2.965	2.349	2.414
1.829	2.802	3.078	2.461	2.534
1.951	3.087	3.277	2.657	2.740
2.073	3.557	3.612	2.968	3.065
2.195	4.223	4.166	3.464	3.543
2.316	5.759	4.950	4.170	4.208
2.438	6.715	6.761	5.835	5.739
(b)				
Distance (m)	Annular_UO ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³⁵ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U) ₂	Annular_(Th- ²³³ U- ²³⁵ U) ₂
0.000	15.064	17.600	13.130	14.100
0.122	8.617	14.595	11.943	12.102
0.244	6.834	10.156	7.145	7.222
0.366	5.453	7.655	5.565	5.679
0.488	4.526	6.756	4.556	4.596
0.610	3.816	5.544	3.675	3.857
0.732	3.677	4.545	3.544	3.391
0.853	3.269	4.045	2.444	3.036
0.975	2.434	3.098	2.747	2.798
1.097	2.434	3.433	2.576	2.622
1.219	2.456	3.433	2.467	2.517
1.341	2.675	3.343	2.476	2.453
1.463	2.565	3.285	2.387	2.435
1.585	2.665	3.342	2.388	2.445
1.707	2.565	3.432	2.469	2.514
1.829	2.667	3.544	2.578	2.634
1.951	3.675	3.454	2.787	2.840
2.073	3.565	3.937	3.068	3.165
2.195	4.565	4.243	3.534	3.643
2.316	5.567	5.430	4.207	4.308
2.438	6.870	5.034	5.835	5.839